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Deliverable D3.3

D3.3 Implementation of the pilot course in Career Management and Entrepreneurship

23/12/2022

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The DocEnhance deliverable no. 3.3 Implementation of the pilot course in Career Management and Entrepreneurship provides an overview over the implementation of the pilot course in Career Management and Entrepreneurship (CM&E) at two universities, in Portugal and Finland. The introduction provides a short overview of the course creation and implementation procedures. The second section is devoted to a short description of piloting universities, namely NOVA University Lisbon in Portugal and Tampere University in Finland. The third section describes the course and offers technical information related to the implementation of the CM&E course in the DocEnhance project. In its first subsection, it describes the content of the course developed in the DocEnhance project, while its second subsection describes the process of its implementation in two EU universities in two loops. The fourth section briefly summarizes the evaluation of the course implementation realized within the DocEnhance project.

Altogether, 62 PhD students at two EU universities participated in two loops of the implementation of the DocEnhance course in Career Management and Entrepreneurship.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The CM&E course was run at two universities. The content of the CM&E course was developed by two universities NOVA and TAU. The courses were adapted to the local situation by an entrepreneurship expert from Innoexc GmbH and two of the trainers from the participating universities. The courses were developed and run through their own Moodle and also uploaded to the DocEnhance platform. After the first implementation an evaluation was done with participants and stakeholders, and the course material on the Docenhance platform was developed further.

2. PILOTING UNIVERSITIES

The CM&E course was piloted for a proof-of-concept by selected partner universities, chosen with the objective of maximizing diversity concerning cultural differences and the developmental stage of their PhD programmes, to assess the applicability of the concept across Europe. The CM&E course was run by NOVA University Lisbon, Portugal and Tampere University, Finland.

2.1 NOVA University Lisbon (Portugal)

The NOVA University of Lisbon (UNL) is a public HEI situated in Lisbon with around 20,000 students and 2,000 PhD candidates. The UNL Doctoral School was launched in 2013 with two specific aims, to reinforce personal and professional development of PhD students through transferable skills training and to establish an open space for Networking and discussion among PhD students and supervisors from the university's nine schools. So far, the doctoral school offers 13 courses for students, open to researchers and non-academic staff, and one course on supervisory skills. The UNL Doctoral School has disseminated its programme and outcomes nationally and internationally and its ambition is now to network with similar institutions in Europe. Additionally, a consortium of HEIs and non-academic organizations (stakeholders in the private and public sectors) represents an employment-oriented opportunity to establish bridges with the world outside academia's walls.

2.2 Tampere University (Finland)

Tampere University (TAU) provides a space for doctoral researchers to develop both their research and innovation activities and transferable skills in multidisciplinary learning and lifelong partnerships. The developed applications of TAU aim to benefit industry, business and the public sector. The university continually strengthens the culture of international collaboration and digitalisation of the campus and promotes sustainable societal renewal, social innovation and spear-head research in health, technology and social sciences. Some 220 doctorates are defended on a yearly basis at TAU. The TAU Doctoral School (est. 2011) is an institutional-level doctoral training expert. The Doctoral School supports the thorough and interdisciplinary academic expertise and employability of all doctoral researchers. Together with doctoral programmes, the School offers excellent, systematic,

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and up-to-date training to all researchers at all career levels. The Doctoral School's courses and other interdisciplinary events bring together the 2200 doctoral-level researchers across all faculties and their 23 doctoral programmes.

3. COURSE DESCRIPTION AND TECHNICAL INFORMATION

The Career Management & Entrepreneurship course aims to support PhD candidates to develop an entrepreneurial mindset, reflect on and help discover possibilities for their future career steps and develop their job hunting skills. The Entrepreneurial mindset is a navigation compass that could help them navigate the job market, identify and seize (entrepreneurial and other) opportunities, both within and outside Academia. The Career Management is a structured approach with different steps for PhD candidates to reflect on personal strengths, weaknesses and life goals, with several steps to find career opportunities that match with your background and wishes.

The target group of the course is all doctoral candidates, with a strong recommendation of multidisciplinary classes to promote interdisciplinary work.

3.1 Description of the DocEnhance course in Career Management and Entrepreneurship

The first module of the CM&E course is a combination of two parts that can be used separately or as an integrated course.

The first part is called **the Entrepreneurial mindset**.

This part has the objectives of providing PhD candidates with an entrepreneurial mindset that will help them navigate the job market, identify, and seize (entrepreneurial and other) opportunities, both within and outside Academia.

The second part is called **Career Management**. This part of the course aims to support the candidates in the different steps in career management and job hunting. The philosophy behind this course is that it provides a general structure and material on career management and its different steps for PhD researchers, but that the contents ideally should be supplemented by local resources:

-ideally the course would be complemented with local material, that describes for example the local networks, the local labor market, job hunting particulars, etc.

-ideally, we recommend using the material in the framework of a locally arranged course in which the participants can discuss their own career plans and reflect on the material and possibly combining this with locally arranged activities, such as visiting a local company or having guests to discuss their career story. Read more about how to use this course at the end of this course, under 'recommendations'

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At the end of the CM&E course, students should be able to:

- Reflect upon personal strengths, weaknesses and life goals
- Develop the next steps in your career thinking and understand how to create and find career opportunities that match with your background and wishes
- Develop critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, communication and self-management skills
- Act upon entrepreneurial ideas and opportunities and transform them into value by mobilizing resources and networks
- Translate their academic skills into transferable skills
- Understand the job-hunting process, within and outside of academia (in part dependent on local resources)

3.2 DocEnhance CM&E course implementation

In March 2021, the DocEnhance consortium put in place the first implementation of the DocEnhance CM&E course (Loop 1), and between May and June 2022 the DocEnhance consortium put in place the second implementation of the DocEnhance CM&E course (Loop 2).

Each course was piloted for proof-of-concept by selected partner universities, chosen with the objective of maximizing diversity concerning cultural differences and the developmental stage of their PhD programmes, in order to assess the applicability of the concept across Europe.

After each pilot course, participants and organisers were invited to complete a brief questionnaire on different aspects of the courses and to provide comments or suggestions for further development and improvement.

The following two tables show the dates, piloting universities and the number of Doctoral candidates (PhD students) at each piloting university. In addition, the form of implementation and language are indicated. Due to the Covid-19 pandemic and different pandemic mitigation measures and pandemic restrictions in both piloting countries the implementation of piloting courses had to follow these circumstances.

Table 1 First round of implementation of the CM&E course (Loop 1)

Course dates	Piloting University	No. Participants	Target group	Form of implementation	Language
19/03/2021-16/04/2021	Tampere University (Finland)	17	Doctoral candidates	Online, 5 weeks with weekly online meetings	English
28/06/2021-06/07/2021	Nova University Lisbon (Portugal)	15	Doctoral candidates	Online: 2 weeks asynchronous and two full days synchronous	English

Due to Covid 19 constraints, the first round was delivered entirely online in both Universities.

The lockdown also contributed to the delay of the first loop, with several adaptations in content. Tampere University had several online meetings (synchronous) with assignments over five weeks. The course was focus mainly on the Career management content. Nova University Lisbon had the first part on Moodle with tasks to develop during two weeks. The local part was intensive, with two full days online (synchronous).

Table 2 Second round of implementation of the CM&E course (Loop 2)

Course dates	Piloting University	No. Participants	Target group	Form of implementation	Language
25/10/2021-10/12/2021	Tampere University	15	Doctoral candidates	Online, 7 weeks with weekly online meetings	English
26/05/2022-02/06/2022	Nova University Lisbon (Portugal)	15	Doctoral candidates	6 days online (asynchronous) and two full days face to face	English

The second round had several changes. At Tampere University, the trainer worked with an entrepreneurship coach to deliver career management and entrepreneurship content; they divided the time with one synchronous session a week: 4 weeks on career management and three weeks on entrepreneurship.

The main change at Nova University Lisbon was the delivery format of the second edition, with the local part delivered face to face and the presence of a guest from the industry to give feedback about the outcomes of the course.

4. EVALUATION OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE CM&E COURSE

This section briefly summarizes the evaluation of CM&E course implementation realized within DocEnhance project.

Overall, the evaluation questionnaire had 43 answers from the 62 students (around 70%). Participants' expectations regarding the learning outcomes of the Career Management course were generally satisfied to a high degree. All participants considered that they achieved their expectations very well or completely.

The students complained about the effort required to complete the course, but were satisfied with the materials and with the course in general.

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REFERENCES

DocEnhance Deliverable No. 4.4 Evaluation of First Implementation of Pilot Courses

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ANNEXES

ANNEX 1 PICTURES FROM CM&E COURSE IMPLEMENTATION

CM&E course implementation at NOVA University Lisbon

Online CM&E course Loop 1

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Face-to-face CM&E course Loop 2